

Artificial Intelligence: Benefit and Risks

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ABSTRACT

this article demonstrate Disadvantage of artificial intelligence to a different field as well as benefits of artificial intelligence. Research to verify that's artificial intelligence is beneficial if its having risks aspect then it's also having advantage and it is safe. Influences virtual physiological state which guide behavior and learning, modulating the emotion that our artificial human "feel" and express. At the aspect of risks factor it may reach to the human level intelligence n may dominate to the human being.

KEYWORDS: Artificial Intelligence, Risks and Benefits

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1. INRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence is a limb of computer science that aims to create intelligent machines. It has become an very important part of the technology industry. Research related to artificial intelligence is supremely technical. The basic and common problems of artificial intelligence include programming computers for certain character such as:

- Generalization
- Reasoning
- Problem solving
- Perception
- Learning

Generalization engineering is a core part of AI research. Machines can often behave OR act and react like humans only if they have bumper information relating to the world. Machine learning and deep learning is also a core part of AI. Learning without any kind of supervision requires an ability to identify patterns in streams of inputs, whereas learning with adequate supervision involves classification and numerical regressions.[3]

An artificial intelligence is branch of cognitive science. Cognitive science is that the scientific study of the human mind and there feeling. it's a extremely knowledge base field, combining concepts and strategies from scientific discipline, applied science, linguistics, philosophy, and neurobiology. the most goal of science is to characterize the character of human data, its forms and content and the way that data is employed, processed, and bought and adopted. Active areas of psychological feature analysis within the Department embrace language, memory, beholding and knowledge, thinking and reasoning, social knowledge, deciding, and

psychological feature development AI give machine with the adapt, reason and supply answer.[5]Creating an AI model of emotion requires very careful consideration of a number of problem domains or "issues". The point to be made here is that these issues OR problem will have to be considered. How one decides to attack a particular one is a different problem.[8]

Humans improve their learning and take more information from observations and interactions and become good over time. The very famous technique to make a computer to mimic a human brain is known as a Neural Network. A neural network contain neurons which resemble the neurons in biological human brain; a neuron takes in info and gives an output. No neural network is as simple as designing a system which takes information and gives output, it has lots of parameters and is much more complicated. Human brain could solve matter to some extent; it becomes harder and harder to solve matter as the complexity increases. Computers can not only analyse the given data, but also they can adapt to it and make their own view through Machine Learning and deep learning. Machine Learning is the part of computer science in which a machine gets trained to solve a particular problem through algorithms.

2. Literature Review:

According to Nadimpalli, M. Artificial intelligence is very important in business application, its used in data analytics generally its uses for AI in business include: Transferring and cross-referencing data; updating files. Consumer behaviour product and forecasting suggestion.[1]

Prof Stephen Hawking, one of Britain's pre-eminent scientists, has said that efforts to create thinking machines pose a threat to our very existence. The development of full artificial intelligence may create problem to human and its very risky to human life. Prof Hawking says the primitive forms of artificial intelligence developed so far have already proved very useful, but vice versa its also dangerous that its use their super intelligence and create something that will out of human control [4]

Discussion of AI (AI) elicits a good vary of feelings. On one finish of the spectrum is concern of job loss spurred by a larva revolution. On the alternative is excitement concerning the overblown prospects of what individuals are able to do with machine augmentation. But Dr. Mark Esposito needs to root the speech communication really. Esposito is that the co-founder of Nexus Frontier technical school and teacher of Harvard's AI in Business: making worth with Machine Learning, a two-day intensive program. instead of considering what can be, he says businesses wanting to adopt AI ought to investigate what already exists. AI has become the most recent technical school hokum everyplace from geographic area to China. however the primary piece of AI, the substitute nerve cell, was developed in 1943 by individual William McCulloch and expert Bruno Walter Pitts. Since then, we've come back a protracted means in our understanding and development of models capable of comprehension, prediction, and analysis.[6] Nick Bostrom the author of the book Superintelligence: paths, dangers, strategies focuses on the development of superintelligence on Earth, Bostrom distinguishes three kinds of super intelligence [7]:

3. ARTIFICIAL NARROW INTELLIGENCE:

Narrow artificial intelligence or weak AI (narrow AI) is a specific type of artificial intelligence in which a technology outperforms humans in some very narrowly defined task or for single domain. Unlike general artificial intelligence (GAI), narrow artificial intelligence OR weak AI focuses on a single subset of cognitive abilities and advances in that spectrum. For example computer chess, Siri, Alexa is good example of narrow Artificial intelligence.

Siri, Cortana, and Google Assistant are all samples of narrow AI, but they are not good samples of a weak AI, as they operate within a limited pre-defined vary of functions. They do not apply parts of minds, they use natural language processing together with predefined rules. They are in particular not examples of strong AI as there are no genuine intelligence nor self-insight. AI researcher Ben Goertzel, on his blog in 2010, stated Siri was "VERY narrow and brittle" evidenced by annoying results if you ask questions outside the limits or beyond limit of the application.[9]

4. ARTIFICIAL GENERAL INTELLIGENCE:

Artificial general intelligence (AGI) refers to a type of distinguished artificial intelligence weak(narrow) and strong AI that is broad in the way that human cognitive systems i.e human mind, intelligence and there emotion are broad, that can do different types of tasks better, and that really simulates the breadth of the human intellect, rather than pointing on more specific or narrower or weak types of tasks. The strong AI almost work or react like human intelligence. The term is used to distinguish various types of artificial intelligence from each other the terms "strong

artificial intelligence (strong AI) or full artificial intelligence(FAI) are also used to discuss broader artificial intelligence goals. Artificial general intelligence is also known as general artificial intelligence.

In Artificial General Intelligence the very challenging thing is to simulate the human brain exactly into the computer, because humans have different behaviour like, laughing, crying, creating things, creating societies doing activities etc. In other words achieving the emotional OR feeling level intelligence is almost impossible in this field. The AGI is most important form Artificial Intelligence to be created, and here comes the Machine Learning and deep learning which is growing very highly, through this technique OR method, the machines could learn themselves and behave all most like human intelligence. Once the Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) functions like a human then, reaching to the level of Super Intelligence (ASI) will not take much time to grow [7].

5. BENEFITS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE:

Artificial intelligence have lots of advantages. One of the benefits is that it has increased the level of performance of physicians at hospital facilities OR in hospital environment. The situation acts in the interest of patients who are look on as customers. The hospital staff can use computer systems or machine specially developed to identify patients who are most at risk and critical situation [2]. Such systems can precisely analyse the specific physiologic problems that various patients found at the hospital could be having and provide proper information about the patient who requires quick action. Through the process, the limited resources found at facilities could be used most efficiently to bring about the best outcomes, about ensuring they have the ability to meet the specific problems that patients may be going through to generally improve their standard of life [3]. Through such a process, computer systems are also able to aid in the process of decision-making and save physicians the time they would have required to consult widely on some of the health problems that the patients could become across. For instance, it has been used to determine the level of interaction of various drugs on patients to see if they have some antagonistic or synergistic effects on one other.[1]

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Artificial intelligence has put into use in areas that would be of great harm to human life. The case, therefore, verify that

companies or industries have the ability to keep safe the lives of many kind of people who work for them through the process of exchange human subjects with artificial intelligence. One of the areas in which such a case is applied is in the mining industry. In such a case, mining companies have been able to create vehicles and machines that can operate underground without being manned by people. In the event of any accidents such as the collapse of the walls of the mines, the different material used in the process of mining could be destroyed, but the general lives of different people involved in the venture could be well-upheld.

6. RISKS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE:

As there are so many advantage and benefits of artificial intelligence in the spite there are so many kinds risks and disadvantage of using artificial intelligence.

There is a chance that it could have far-reaching negative point upon various people who come into contact with these, either directly or indirectly. One of the uses that could be identified with the use of such technology is that it is only as better as the data put into it. Where the given data provides for a chance of having a misleading outcome, there is a high chance that it could bring about serious problems to that effect [10]. For instance, where a given hospital facility has installed a system that classifies cancer as high-priority, it automatically declassifies pneumonia as high priority, unless the case is clearly stated too. In this sort of scenario, it creates important matter wherever it fails to produce for the patients World Health Organization area unit delivered to it with the high level of urgency they'd want for the various health issues they need to be handled within the best manner. A patient World Health Organization happens to suffer from respiratory disorder might, therefore, be exposed to a high level of inflated severity of the given drawback that he is also suffering. Such a case would, therefore, increase the possibilities of a private succumbing to the terribly health issue that would, otherwise, be handled. The patient, as a client would lack the chance to profit well from services offered at the consultation room.

Another risk of An AI is that, by commutation human subjects, it brings within the general drawback of golf stroke individuals out of labor its mean it creating individuals idle. firms that build use of computing depends on reducing the quantity of human subjects with whom they're concerned. The case, therefore, brings in some major issues given the actual fact that it reduces the quantity of individuals World Health Organization have the prospect of taking advantage of the various employment opportunities that would be convey by such firms. Through such a method, there's a high probability that given firms might fail to make the terribly level of economic development that may be fascinating in a neighborhood [5]. The case would clearly show that such entities would lack the flexibility to produce a high level of employment that may be fascinating. Employment would increase the quantity of income that folks would be exposed to, for the sake of guaranteeing that they need the flexibility to satisfy a number of their wants. Through the method, firms might lack the capability to own a detailed engagement

with their customers for the aim of guaranteeing their wants area unit met.

Conclusion:

An idea and points that have been centred here is limited only to the content of what an Artificial Intelligence (AI) actually is? And what are its outcome if this AI system becomes powerful then human. The predictions cannot be create absolutely about this powerful system, what if it turns out friendly, will it change the whole humanity and will be helpful to mankind. Or what if it seems unfriendly and would destroy mankind and harm to the mankind. The exact result cannot be forecast and even the futurists and scientists are still on their research of how to control the effect of the most powerful AI system. The first super-intelligent system that mankind would create, it may be the last invention of mankind, and whatever human will teach to AI, probably the human would get to teach it only single time, because after that at some point they will become very intelligent and would re-made themselves. Some of the solutions that depicted in this paper concerning to the Nick Bostrom's book are not considered as enough solutions to the matter. There were many suggestions to the solutions set out in this book. There are some organizations who unit engaged on the long run impact of the AI system.

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